

Radio SED and images of the 116 young UC HII regions

Radio SED

C-band image

X-band image

K-band image

Fig. B.1: Figures of the best-fitting SEDs and the radio images in C-band (CORNISH), X-band, and K-band observations for the full sample of 116 young H II regions. Panel (a): Radio SED and best-fitting model for each source in the sample. The SED shows the free-free emission fit to flux density points between 1 and 26 GHz for a single compact source, while the extended source has the best fit to flux density points between 1 and 11 GHz as their K-band flux measurements are not reliable owing to the shortage of short baseline spacings. The uncertainties on flux measurements of these points are used to constrain the fitting process and to obtain the best estimate. The best-fitting results of electron density n_e (cm^{-3}) and physical diameter $diam$ (pc) for each source are shown in the upper-left corner of each figure. Panels (b), (c) and (d): Radio images in C-band, X-band, and K-band marked with the positions of the young UCHII regions in each image, including single-component compact sources, extended sources, and cluster sources. The C-band images are taken from the CORNISH survey and are used to compare with the images at X-band in this work as the X-band observations have comparable beam sizes to those of the CORNISH survey. For some sources, the K-band images are not shown because of the poor quality of observational data at K-band. The line polygons in the C-band images shown for some sources are similar to the defined region in the CORNISH survey. The line polygons in the X-band images shown for some sources refer to the manually drawn emission regions used to measure the observational results following the same strategy in CORNISH survey. The white contour levels in the images are equally spaced by 5σ and start at a level of 5σ . The image size of each target is shown in the upper-middle part of each image. The beam sizes for C-band ($1.5''$), X-band ($\sim 1.7''$), and K-band ($0.7''$) are shown in the lower-left corner of each image.